

The impact of direct and indirect taxation on poverty: The case study of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: This research investigates the impact of direct and indirect taxes on poverty in Pakistan, recognizing poverty as a global issue prevalent across developed, developing, and underdeveloped nations. Utilizing time series data spanning from the first quarter of 2000 to the fourth quarter of 2021, we employed an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to assess short-term and long-term relationships between poverty and various tax variables including sales taxes, custom taxes, income taxes, and federal excise duties. Additionally, inflation and unemployment were incorporated as control variables in the analysis. By employing Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) to determine variable lags and conduct long-run bound tests to evaluate the significance of relationships, our findings highlight a significant association between poverty and sales taxes, federal excise duties, and income taxes. Custom taxes were found to have no significant impact on poverty in the long run but increased poverty in the short term, while sales taxes and income taxes exhibited short-term effects on poverty. Overall, indirect taxes were identified as contributing to increased poverty levels in the short term. These results underscore the importance of understanding the nuanced impacts of taxation policies on poverty dynamics, emphasizing the role of targeted interventions in poverty alleviation efforts in Pakistan.

Keywords: Indirect Taxation, Impact on Poverty, Case Study Of Pakistan,

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1. Introduction

Developing and underdeveloped countries grapple with a myriad of challenges, among which poverty stands as a formidable obstacle to progress and prosperity. Poverty, a multifaceted phenomenon with myriad determinants, ensnares underdeveloped nations in a vicious cycle of economic stagnation and social distress. Its ramifications extend beyond economic constraints, permeating into various facets of society and hindering overall growth and development. Indeed, poverty serves as a root cause underlying a host of other societal issues, including heightened crime rates, pervasive corruption, diminished life expectancy, and compromised human capital. To dissect the intricate relationship between poverty and its determinants, this study focuses on key variables such as income tax, sales taxes, federal excise duty, and custom taxes, with inflation and unemployment serving as control variables. Taxes, delineated into direct (e.g., income tax) and indirect (e.g., sales tax, custom duty, federal excise duty) categories, play a pivotal role in shaping the

economic landscape of nations. In Pakistan, indirect taxes dominate the tax landscape, comprising 65% of total taxes, with sales tax, excise duty, and customs duty being the primary contributors. Notably, the trajectory of these tax components has exhibited fluctuations over time, with sales tax demonstrating a steady increase from 2014 to 2019, while excise and customs duties have seen comparatively modest growth. Conversely, direct taxes initially ascended but witnessed a decline in 2019, as per data from the State Bank of Pakistan and the Federal Board of Revenue (FBR). Moreover, poverty, exacerbated by factors such as inflation, unemployment, and budget deficits, perpetuates a cycle of economic hardship within a nation. The ensuing study endeavors to shed light on the nuanced interplay between poverty and its determinants, with a particular focus on the role of taxation policies in Pakistan's socioeconomic landscape.

2. Literature Review

Poverty, a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, encompasses a spectrum of deprivation extending beyond mere material scarcity. It manifests in various forms, from lacking access to essentials like food, clean water, healthcare, clothing, and shelter, to confronting systemic barriers that limit opportunities for socioeconomic advancement. Poverty is inherently subjective and objective, with definitions spanning both relative and absolute terms. Early scholars such as Rowntree (1901) and Orshansk (1965) conceptualized poverty in absolute terms, defining it as the deprivation of basic necessities like food, shelter, and clothing. In contrast, Townsend (1970) introduced the concept of relative poverty, characterized by a lack of goods and services considered customary or accessible to the majority within a society. Similarly, Goedhart et al. (1977) emphasized poverty as insufficient income to meet basic needs. Taxation, as posited by Adam Smith in 1776, should adhere to four principles: the ability to pay principle, certainty, cost-effectiveness in administration and collection, and convenience for taxpayers. Our focus aligns with the ability to pay principle, which stipulates that taxation should be proportionate to one's financial capacity. However, the current taxation structure, particularly the imposition of sales taxes and value-added tax (VAT) on essential goods, disproportionately burdens the middle and lower classes. Given that a significant portion of their income is allocated to basic necessities, the regressive nature of sales taxes exacerbates their financial strain, leaving minimal resources for other expenses. In contrast, the affluent segments of society, who allocate a smaller proportion of their income to essentials, bear a lesser tax burden relative to their financial capacity. This glaring disparity underscores the inequities inherent in the current tax regime, exacerbating the economic vulnerabilities faced by low and middle-income individuals and families.

Ali and Ali (2018) conducted a comprehensive study on the determinants of poverty in Pakistan, incorporating variables such as exchange rate, inflation, unemployment rate, budget deficit, and government expenditure. Employing Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique and utilizing data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and the World Economy Pk, they observed a positive relationship between poverty and inflation, unemployment, and exchange rate. The impact of exchange rate on poverty was found to be indirect through various factors, while government expenditure and budget deficit exhibited a negative correlation with poverty. Their study highlighted the significance of

addressing inflation, unemployment, and exchange rate fluctuations in poverty alleviation efforts, recommending policy measures such as bolstering the agriculture sector, enhancing healthcare access for the impoverished, and implementing progressive taxation to redistribute wealth. Adukonu and Abebrese (2017) investigated the relative influence of various taxes on poverty levels in Ghana. Utilizing Johansen cointegration techniques and secondary data from the Institute of Statistics, ISSER, and Ghana Revenue Authority, they examined the impact of personal remittances received, taxes on income and property, import taxes, export taxes, and taxes on domestic goods. Their findings revealed that while direct taxes like income tax had a limited effect on poverty, indirect taxes or consumption-related taxes exacerbated poverty in the long run. They recommended the implementation of tax policies aimed at reducing indirect taxes such as sales tax, consumption tax, and Value Added Tax (VAT) to mitigate poverty in Ghana. In the context of Nigeria, the impact of Value Added Tax (VAT) on poverty reduction was explored by a study focusing on its direct and indirect effects on the economy. The research indicated a significant and positive relationship between VAT and economic growth, with VAT revenue playing a crucial role in poverty reduction, particularly if the taxation on goods consumed by the affluent surpasses that on goods consumed by the impoverished.

Ismaeel (2013) delved into the impact of direct and indirect taxation on consumer behavior, employing theoretical analysis to elucidate the effects of different tax structures. The study revealed that while indirect taxes afford governments greater control due to their flexibility in adjustment, direct taxes are perceived as more equitable. However, indirect taxes were found to be regressive, impacting consumers' purchasing power differently. This underscores the complexity of taxation policies and their varying implications on consumer welfare and economic dynamics. Overall, the reviewed studies underscore the intricate relationship between taxation policies and poverty dynamics, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address the multifaceted nature of poverty in diverse socio-economic contexts.

3. Econometric Model and Methodology

In this study, we employed the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to analyze the relationship between variables. The ARDL model is particularly suitable when the dependent variable is influenced by its own past values as well as other explanatory variables. This modeling approach has been utilized in similar research contexts, such as the examination of the impact of indirect taxes on economic growth by Ilaboya and Mgbame (2012). Additionally, Ogboi and Charles (2014) employed Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to investigate the effects of Value Added Tax (VAT) on poverty and economic growth. Similarly, Adukonu and Abebrese (2017) utilized both ARDL and DFGLS methods to explore the impact of various taxes on poverty in Ghana. In our study, we utilized both short-run (SR) and long-run (LR) ARDL models to examine the dynamics between variables and their effects on poverty in our context.

$$POV_t = CUST_t + INCOMET_t + SALT_t + FED_t \quad (1)$$

OR

$$POV_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CUST_t + \beta_2 INCOMET_t + \beta_3 SALT_t + \beta_4 FED_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Where POV is poverty level

CUST is a custom tax

INCOME is income tax

SAL is sales tax

FED is the federal excise duty

Where β_0 is the intercept

β_1 , β_2 , β_3 and β_4 are coefficients of CUST, INCOMET, SALT and FED respectively.

μ is the residual term or error term.

CUST, SALT and FED are indirect taxes. INCOME is a direct tax.

ARDL MODEL FORM

$$POV_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=0}^1 \beta POV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta LFED_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 \theta LCUS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 \pi LINCOM_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 \lambda LSAL_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 shows that poverty at time t is the function of previous year poverty, federal excise duty, current and previous year custom duty, income tax, current and previous year sales tax. We used inflation and unemployment as control variables in our model.

4. Results

Unit Root (ADF) Test

Based on first difference probability values; custom taxes, inflation and income taxes are stationary at 5% significant level. Federal excise duty, sale taxes and unemployment are stationary at level at 5% significant level. We can see the variables under analysis are mixed stationary, so we will apply ARDL model.

Table 1 Unit Root Test

Variable	Level prob	First diff prob	Second diff Prob	Order of Integration
Lcus_t	0.8034	0.017	--	I(1)
Linf	0.7845	0.0456	--	I(1)
Lincome_t	0.7869	0.0249	--	I(1)
Lfed	0.0458	--	--	I(0)
Lsal_t	0.0427	--	--	I(0)
Lunem	0.0349	--	--	I(0)

Long Run Bound Test

Long run bound test is used to check whether there is long run relationship between variables or not. If the F-statistics value fall below the value of lower bound test it means that there is no cointegration and if the F-statistics value exceed the upper bound value it means that cointegration exist.

Table 2 Boud Test

F-Bounds Test			Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship	
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	4.8954	10%	2.08	3
k	5	5%	2.4	3.59
		2.5%	2.78	3.38
		1%	3.09	4.27

Table 1 displays the results of the bound test conducted to ascertain the presence of a long-run relationship. This test determines the existence of such a relationship based on the value of the F-statistic. If the F-statistic exceeds the upper range mean, it indicates a long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. In this instance, the F-statistic value is calculated as 4.89, surpassing the upper range of 3.59 at a 5% significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that no long-run relationship exists is rejected. Consequently, based on the bound test results, it is established that a long-run relationship indeed exists among the independent variables (sales tax, FED, custom duty, income tax) and the dependent variable (poverty).

Error Correction Term

Table 2 presents the error correction term, which serves as an indicator of the converging or diverging tendencies of variables in the long run towards equilibrium. A

negative error correction term signifies convergence, while a positive term indicates divergence. Ideally, the value of the error correction term should fall between 0 and -1 to indicate convergence in the long run. In this case, the error correction term (ECM) is calculated as -0.0459, indicating a converging trend in the long run. Notably, the significant value of -6.44 reinforces the reliability of this convergence finding.

Table 3 ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LPOV(-1))	0.626416	0.065950	9.195153	0.0000
D(LSAL_T)	0.289319	0.057278	5.051162	0.0000
D(LSAL_T(-1))	0.202219	0.059675	3.388663	0.0012
D(LIND_T)	0.534867	0.091510	5.844917	0.0000
D(LIND_T(-1))	0.379203	0.091248	4.155722	0.0001
D(LINCOME_T)	-0.050990	0.030879	-1.651299	0.4033
D(LCUS_T)	0.157651	0.034587	4.558064	0.0430
D(LCUS_T(-1))	-0.129979	0.033729	-3.853649	0.0303
D(LFED)	-0.066547	0.025942	-2.565231	0.0125
ConitEq(-1)	-0.04596	0.007122	-6.447243	0.0000
R-squared	0.773059	Mean dependent var		-0.005253
Adjusted R-squared	0.758512	S.D. dependent var		0.004606
S.E. of regression	0.002264	Akaike info criterion		-9.274917
Sum squared resid	0.000400	Schwarz criterion		-9.101287
Log likelihood	395.5465	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-9.205119
Durbin-Watson stat	2.087408			

The results of the short-run Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model reveal distinct coefficient values for various variables. The initial coefficient value of 0.62 indicates a positive relationship between current-year poverty and the poverty level of the previous year. This suggests that a one-unit increase in last year's poverty level contributes to a 0.62-unit rise in the current poverty level, highlighting the enduring impact of poverty over time. This underscores the importance of breaking the vicious cycle of poverty through strategic interventions such as investment and subsidies. Federal Excise Duty, an indirect tax, exhibits a coefficient value of -0.06, indicating that a one-unit increase in Federal Excise Duty leads to a modest 0.06-unit decrease in poverty. This tax, primarily imposed on imported goods, affects the business class more than the poor, as businesses typically absorb the tax rather than passing it on to consumers. Sales taxes, which constitute a significant portion of total taxes at 44%, demonstrate a coefficient value of 0.28, suggesting that a one-unit increase in sales taxes results in a 0.28-unit rise in poverty in the short run. Given that sales taxes are indirect and ultimately borne by the end consumer through increased prices, particularly impacting those who spend a large portion of their income on basic necessities. Custom taxes, with a coefficient value of 0.15, indicate that a one-unit increase in custom taxes leads to a 0.15-unit increase in poverty. The impact of custom taxes on poverty varies depending on the type of goods taxed, with luxury items having a lower impact compared to essential goods, which may disproportionately affect the middle

and lower-income classes. Income taxes exhibit a coefficient value of -0.050, suggesting that a one-unit increase in income taxes results in a modest 0.050-unit decrease in poverty in the short run. However, the impact of income taxes on poverty is considered insignificant in the short run, as they primarily affect the same individuals on whom they are imposed.

Table 4 Cointegration Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LSAL_T	0.651297	0.556069	1.171252	0.0156
LIND_T	1.216933	0.751958	1.618352	0.0102
LINCOME_T	-0.503160	0.329970	-2.009759	0.0144
LCUS_T	0.436623	0.229329	1.903916	0.0612
LINF	0.666726	0.002771	2.322881	0.0154
LFED	0.041050	0.301599	2.125506	0.0372
LUNEM	0.003220	0.014968	0.215120	0.0133
C	2.121272	0.418848	5.064543	0.0000

Table 4 presents the long-run findings of the study. In the long run, the ARDL model indicates that a one-unit rise in customs duty corresponds to a 0.43-unit increase in poverty; however, this impact is deemed insignificant. Conversely, a one-unit increase in income taxes results in a notable 0.50-unit decrease in poverty, indicating a more substantial effect on poverty reduction in the long run compared to the short run. Income taxes contribute to poverty reduction through their progressive nature and redistribution effects, exemplified by the taxation of higher incomes. This progressive taxation system can significantly alleviate poverty over an extended timeframe. Moreover, a one-unit increase in sales taxes leads to a 0.65-unit increase in poverty in the long run, showcasing a higher percentage impact compared to the short run. Similarly, a one-unit increase in Federal Excise Duty (FED) raises poverty by 0.64 units over the long run. Additionally, an increase in unemployment by one unit corresponds to a 0.003-unit increase in poverty levels, while a one-unit increase in the inflation rate raises the poverty level by 0.66 units. These findings elucidate the nuanced and lasting effects of various economic factors on poverty levels over an extended period, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive and sustainable policy measures for poverty alleviation.

The independent variables exhibited varying effects on the dependent variable in both the short and long run, showcasing distinct behaviors in the ARDL model. Control variables, namely inflation and unemployment, were found to have no significant impact on poverty in the short run, whereas the Long-run ARDL results revealed that both inflation and unemployment contributed to increased poverty over time. In the short run, custom duty positively affected poverty, albeit insignificantly in the long run, where its impact on poverty was deemed negligible. Specifically, a one-unit increase in custom duty led to a 0.15-unit increase in poverty in the short run. Indirect taxes had a substantial impact on poverty, with a 0.53-unit increase in the short run and a more pronounced 1.21-unit increase in the long run, indicating a persistent rise in poverty across both timeframes.

Regarding direct taxes, income taxes displayed no significant impact on poverty in the short run but exhibited a poverty-reducing effect of 0.50 units in the long run,

attributable to their progressive nature and redistribution effects. Conversely, federal excise duty demonstrated a minor poverty-alleviating impact of 0.06 units in the short run and a slightly higher poverty-increasing effect of 0.04 units in the long run per one-unit increase in duty. Sales taxes were found to significantly increase poverty, with a 0.28-unit rise in the short run and a more pronounced 0.65-unit increase in the long run, indicating a persistent exacerbation of poverty levels. Consistent with findings from Adukonu and Abebrese (2017), our results suggest that direct taxes tend to decrease poverty while indirect taxes tend to increase it. Moreover, indirect regressive taxes disproportionately affect poverty in rural areas and among farmers, constraining disposable income and consumer spending incentives. Specifically, consumer spending exhibits a 91% response to indirect taxes, highlighting their significant impact on consumption patterns. Additionally, General Sales Taxes (GST) have been noted to positively impact farmers by increasing the prices of their products, as observed by Tharani and Ahmed (2017).

5. Conclusion & Recommendations

Our primary objective was to assess the impact of both direct and indirect taxation on poverty. Analyzing the results of short-run ARDL, we identified a short-term relationship between various taxes and poverty. Similarly, from our long-run ARDL analysis and long-run bound test, we inferred a sustained connection between taxes and poverty over time. By examining the coefficient values of different variables, we were able to address our research question effectively. Specifically, we found that sales taxes exert an influence on poverty in both the short and long term, with a greater impact observed in the long run. The relationship between sales taxes and poverty was deemed significant in both temporal contexts, with an increase in sales taxes correlating with a rise in poverty levels. Additionally, the impact of income taxes on poverty was deemed significant, contributing to increased poverty in the long run while displaying no significant impact in the short run. Furthermore, the effects of custom duty and federal excise taxes were also found to be significant. Federal excise duty was observed to increase poverty in the long run but decrease it in the short run, while custom duty resulted in increased poverty in the short run.

Our findings underscore the necessity of tax policies that alleviate the burden on low-income and middle-class households, given their substantial expenditure on consumption goods and services. In Pakistan, where sales taxes constitute a considerable 44% of total taxes, primarily imposed on essential commodities such as crops and cereals, the regressive nature of these taxes disproportionately affects the impoverished. Direct taxes should constitute a significant portion of total taxes, with an emphasis on progressive taxation to mitigate poverty. However, it is imperative to strike a balance in increasing direct taxes without disincentivizing labor. Moreover, efforts to combat inflation and unemployment, our control variables, should be prioritized through production-oriented projects that stimulate job creation and mitigate demand-pull inflation in the long run. In light of the prevalent reliance on indirect taxation for revenue generation in developing and underdeveloped countries, policymakers must implement measures to curtail tax evasion, particularly in income tax, which poses a higher risk of non-compliance through record concealment. While tax revenue, whether from direct or indirect sources, can spur economic growth if allocated to developmental projects, it is often directed towards current

expenditures and foreign debt repayment in such economies. Consequently, a lack of substantial developmental expenditure, coupled with a heavy tax burden on households, may impede budget allocation for crucial developmental and investment initiatives. Therefore, while both direct and indirect taxation policies can be effective in revenue collection, they should be inherently progressive in nature to promote equitable economic growth and poverty alleviation.

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